

First synthesis of ventinone A and structural ambiguity of ventinone B

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Manuscript received 31 December 2009, accepted 28 January 2010

Abstract : Ventinone A, a naturally occurring 1,4-dihydroxyanthraquinone has been synthesized in two steps from known compounds via a Hauser annulation. The same strategy, when applied to the synthesis of ventinone B, reveals that the proposed structure of ventinone B is identical with that of 4-methyl ether of erythroglaucon.

Keywords : Ventinone A, ventinone B, synthesis.

Introduction

1,4-Dihydroxyanthraquinones (quinizarins) are prevalent in natural products as well as synthetic materials^{1,2}. They are also integral structural parts of many pharmaceutical agents such as anthracyclines (e.g. doxorubicin (1)), bis(dialkylamino)anthraquinones (e.g. mitoxantrone (2)) and bioactive natural products like dynemicin A (3). Recently, a relatively simple quinizarin analog (i.e., 4) of mensacarcin³ has been reported to exhibit *in vitro* inhibitory effects on lung carcinoma cells of line A549. The degree of the effect increases with number of free phenolic OH groups, and the presence of the side-chain ep-

oxide functionality is not crucial for the biological activity. In view of the above findings on quinizarins, we selected ventinone A (5) and B (6) for the synthetic study, which remained unexplored till date. Both the compounds were isolated from roots of *Ventilago maderaspatana*^{4a}. Ventinone A (5) is structurally unique in having two methyl substituents in the same ring. Rao *et al.* reported isolation of ventinone B (6) from roots of *Ventilago maderaspatana* and assigned its structure 6 as shown in Scheme 1^{4a}. However, the structure of ventinone B has been questioned by Simoneu and Brassard on the basis of the synthesis of the proposed structure^{4b}.

Fig. 1. Structures of bioactive quinizarins.

The NMR data for the synthesized compound were not in agreement with the reported data. In order to achieve the synthesis of the title compounds, we considered applications of our recent synthesis^{5a} of quinizarins by the Hauser annulation^{5b}. Herein, we report synthesis of ventinone A (5) in 2 steps and propose correction of the originally assigned structure of ventinone B (6).

Results and discussion

The retrosynthesis of ventinones 5 and 6 with the Hauser annulation led to identification of 3-phenylsulfanylphthalide (7a)⁶ as the common synthon. With appropriate quinone Michael acceptors, both the ventinones 5 and 6 could be accessed from the same phthalide 7a. Selective demethylation of the annulation product of phthalide 7a and quinone 8⁷ should give ventinone A (5). Similar annulation of 7a with 9⁸ should directly provide ventinone B (6).

The synthesis of phthalide 7a commenced from 3,5-dihydroxybenzoic acid (10). In four known steps⁶ (esterification, *O*-methylation, formylation, phenylsulfanylation), the acid 10 was converted to phthalide 7a (Scheme 2). Oxidation of 7a with hydrogen peroxide in acetic acid afforded phthalide sulfone 7b. The Hauser annulation of benzoquinone 8 with phthalide 7a in the presence of lithium *tert*-butoxide at -60 °C gave product 11 in 10% yield. Annulation of benzoquinone 9 with 3-phenylsul-

fanylphthalide 7a provided a mixture of quinizarins 6a and 6b in very poor yield (~10%). In view of the poor yield, the reactivity of the corresponding sulfone i.e. 3-phenylsulfanylphthalide 7b in the place of 7a was examined.

The Hauser annulation of 3-phenylsulfanylphthalide 7b, prepared by oxidation of 7a (Scheme 2), with benzoquinone 8 gave quinizarin 11 in 52% yield. Four singlets at δ 14.13, 13.56, 4.04 and 4.00 in its ¹H NMR spectrum were in complete agreement with the formation of compound 11. Demethylation of 11 with a refluxing mixture of acetic acid and hydrobromic acid gave ventinone A (5) in 53% yield. The presence of signals corresponding to 3 hydrogen bonded protons at δ 12.49, 12.99 and 13.67 confirmed the formation of ventinone A. The NMR data (Table 1) also matched with the reported data for natural product^{4a}. For the synthesis of ventinone B (6), annulation of phthalide sulfone 7b with quinone 9 was conducted in the presence of lithium *tert*-butoxide at -60 °C. It provided an inseparable ~1 : 1 (as determined by a HPLC analysis) mixture of quinizarins 6a and 6b in 30% yield. One set of the ¹H and ¹³C NMR data of the mixture perfectly matched with those of 4-methyl ether of erythroglaucin, as reported by Simoneu and Brassard^{4b}, and not with the originally reported values^{4a} of ventinone B (6). In essence, the proposed structure of ventinone B (6) is to be corrected. On the basis of the established chemistry of the Hauser annulation, we conclude that the second product has the structure 6b.

Scheme 1. Retrosynthetic analysis of ventinone A and B.

Scheme 2⁶. Synthesis of phthalides 7.

Scheme 3. Synthesis of ventinone A and B.

Table 1. Data for natural and synthetic ventinone A

	Natural ventinone A (5)	Synthetic ventinone A (5)
M.p.	188 °C	185–186 °C
¹ H NMR	(90 MHz, CDCl ₃): 13.59 (1H, s), 12.89 (1H, s), 12.33 (1H, s), 7.70 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 2.0 Hz), 6.69 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 2.0 Hz), 4.03 (3H, s), 2.18 (6H, s)	(200 MHz, CDCl ₃): 13.67 (1H, s), 12.99 (1H, s), 12.49 (1H, s), 7.42 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 2.6 Hz), 6.70 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 2.6 Hz), 3.94 (3H, s), 2.32 (6H, s)
ν_{\max}	(CHCl ₃ , cm ⁻¹): 3430, 1595, 1400, 1300	(KBr, cm ⁻¹): 3424, 1602, 1390, 1162
¹³ C NMR	Not reported	(400 MHz, CDCl ₃): 166.3, 165.0, 157.9, 156.7, 138.7, 138.0, 135.2, 129.0, 127.4, 127.1, 110.6, 109.2, 107.0, 106.8, 56.0, 12.5, 12.5

Conclusion :

The first synthesis of ventinone A (5) has been accomplished in only two steps from known compounds via Hauser annulation. Extension of the strategy to ventinone B (6) reveals error in the originally proposed structure.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on a Thermo Nicolet Nexus 870 FT-IR spectrophotometers using KBr pellet and only the characteristic, strong and medium peaks are presented. ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded on a 200 MHz or 400 MHz spectrometer (Bruker) as solution in CDCl₃ with residual

CHCl₃ as the internal standard. Chemical shifts are expressed in δ unit and coupling constant in Hz. Mass spectra were taken using a VG Autospec M mass spectrometer. Dry solvents used for reactions were purified, before use, according to the standard procedure. All solvents for chromatography were distilled prior to use. Columns were prepared with silica gel (60–120 or 230–400 mesh).

General procedure for annulation reaction :

To a stirred solution of lithium *t*-butoxide (9.84 mmol) in THF (40 mL) at -60 °C (chloroform/liquid N₂ bath) under an inert atmosphere a solution of a phthalide (3.28 mmol) in THF (5 mL) was added. The resulting yellowish solution was stirred at -60 °C for 25 min, after which a solution of a Michael acceptor (1.0–1.5 equiv. unless otherwise stated) in THF (5 mL) was added to it. The cooling bath was removed after about 1 h at -60 °C and the reaction mixture was brought to room temperature over a period of 1 h and further stirred for 3 h. The reaction was then quenched with 10% aq. NH₄Cl (15 mL) and the resulting solution was concentrated. An orange solid appeared. This was filtered and washed with 1 : 1 mixture (20 mL) of diethyl ether and petroleum ether. Otherwise, the residue was diluted with ethyl acetate (50 mL) and the layers were separated. The aqueous layer was extracted with ethyl acetate (3 × 25 mL). The combined extracts were washed with H₂O (15 mL), brine (15 mL), dried (anhydrous Na₂SO₄), and concentrated under reduced pressure. The crude product was purified by column chromatography on silica gel or by recrystallization to obtain a pure product.

Ventinone A (5) : Anthraquinone **11** (100 mg, 0.30 mmol) was dissolved in a solution of acetic acid (5 mL) and 42% aqueous HBr (5 mL). The mixture was heated at reflux for 8 h. It was then cooled and extracted with ethyl acetate (2 × 50 mL). The combined extracts were then washed successively with water (20 mL), saturated solution of sodium bicarbonate (20 mL), brine (20 mL), dried (anhydrous Na₂SO₄), filtered and concentrated under reduced pressure. The resulting residue was purified by column chromatography on silica gel to furnish pure ventinone A (**5**) (50 mg, 53%). $R_f = 0.7$ (1 : 3 ethyl acetate/petroleum ether); m.p. 185–186 °C; ν_{\max} (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3424, 1602, 1390, 1162; ¹H NMR (200 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 13.67 (1H, s), 12.99 (1H, s), 12.49 (1H, s), 7.42 (1H, d, J 2.6 Hz), 6.70 (1H, d, J 2.6 Hz), 3.94 (3H, s), 2.32 (6H, s); ¹³C NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 166.3, 165.0, 157.9, 156.7, 138.7, 138.0, 135.2, 129.0, 127.4, 127.1, 110.6, 109.2, 107.0, 106.8, 56.0, 12.5, 12.5.

1,4-Dihydroxy-6,8-dimethoxy-2-methylanthraquinone (6a) and **1,4-dihydroxy-5,7-dimethoxy-2-methylanthraquinone (6b)** : These compounds were obtained in 30% yield as orange red solid mixture by the reaction between 2-methyl-*p*-benzoquinone and **7b**, according to the general procedure for annulation reaction. The crude product could not be separated by column chromatography. $R_f = 0.6$ (1 : 3 ethyl acetate/petroleum ether); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 13.87 (1H, s), 13.48 (1H, s), 13.25 (1H, s), 12.91 (1H, s), 7.52–7.55 (2H, m), 7.15 (1H, s), 7.09 (1H, s), 6.81 (2H, d, J 2.4 Hz), 4.10 (3H, s), 4.08 (3H, s), 4.04 (3H, s), 4.00 (3H, s), 2.36 (3H, s), 2.35 (3H, s).

1,4-Dihydroxy-5,7-dimethoxy-2,3-dimethylanthraquinone (11) : This compound was prepared as a red solid in 52% yield by the reaction between benzoquinone **9** and phthalide **7b**, according to the general procedure for annulation reaction. The crude product was purified

by column chromatography on silica gel to furnish pure **11**. $R_f = 0.6$ (1 : 5 ethyl acetate/petroleum ether); m.p. 285–287 °C; ν_{\max} (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3534, 2362, 1650, 1459, 1259, 1043, 754; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 14.14 (1H, s), 13.56 (1H, s), 7.53 (1H, d, $J = 2$ Hz), 6.79 (1H, d, $J = 2$ Hz), 4.04 (3H, s), 4.00 (3H, s), 2.32 (3H, s), 2.30 (3H, s); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 186.12, 186.09, 165.1, 163.0, 156.9, 139.5, 137.8, 136.2, 115.7, 110.2, 109.8, 104.8, 103.0, 56.7, 56.1, 12.8, 12.4 (one carbon is missing); HRMS *m/e* calcd. for C₁₈H₁₇O₆ (MH)⁺ 329.1025, found 329.1029.

Acknowledgement

This research was supported by the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research (CSIR), New Delhi. SR is thankful to the CSIR for her research fellowship. The 400 MHz NMR instrument was purchased under FIST program of the DST, New Delhi.

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